

5G/6G Technology Capabilities Designed for Secure Edge Network: Use Cases of Turkcell

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Abstract—There is no doubt that 5G and 6G technologies coupled with secure edge network capabilities play crucial roles in the evolution of Industry 4.0 and emerging Industry 5.0. In Industry 4.0, 5G enhances smart manufacturing by enabling ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), massive machine-type communication (mMTC), and enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB). These features support real-time monitoring, automation, edge computing, and data exchange across interconnected devices and systems to improve industrial efficiency and productivity. With Industry 5.0, which focuses on human-machine collaboration, 5G continues to be vital, but the advent of 6G will bring even greater capabilities. 6G is expected to offer a higher level of autonomy and advanced artificial intelligence integration by facilitating seamless interaction between humans, machines as well as intelligent systems. This will enable more sophisticated applications, such as advanced robotics, virtual and augmented reality experiences, further connected driving innovations, and also the symbiosis between humans and technology, built on ubiquitous connectivity. From a leading mobile network operator perspective, in this paper, we delve into how 5G technology, empowered with secure edge networks, can transform XR communication, vehicular communication, and also UAV-based aerial communication while enabling safer, more reliable, and more efficient systems in the smart technology campuses.

Index Terms—Smart mobility, smart campus, next-generation mobile communications (5G/6G), secure edge network.

I. INTRODUCTION

The convergence of cutting-edge communication technologies such as 5G and 6G with secure edge network infrastructures is driving a new wave of innovation in both Industry 4.0 and the emerging Industry 5.0. Industry 4.0 has been characterized by the increasing digitalization of manufacturing, where smart factories leverage advanced sensors, interconnected devices, and real-time data analytics to optimize processes, improve productivity, and enhance decision-making. The deployment of 5G networks has significantly accelerated this transformation by enabling ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), massive machine-type communication (mMTC), and enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), which together support automation, edge computing, and seamless data exchange in industrial and private environments.

As industries currently evolve towards Industry 5.0, there is a growing emphasis on human-machine collaboration, with technology acting as a facilitator of more complex interactions between humans, machines, and intelligent systems. In this context, 6G is expected to build on the foundation established by 5G, offering unprecedented levels of connectivity, autonomy, and artificial intelligence integration. With

the 6G technology, applications will extend beyond traditional manufacturing to more advanced fields such as robotics, extended reality (XR), connected vehicles, and UAV-based aerial communications, creating opportunities for more immersive, responsive, as well as efficient industrial ecosystems [1].

The applications of Beyond 5G technology will extend beyond traditional manufacturing sectors to include advanced robotics, where machines will not only be automated but also equipped with cognitive capabilities that allow them to collaborate closely with human workers. In extended reality (XR) environments, next-generation communication technologies will offer the bandwidth and responsiveness required to create immersive virtual and augmented reality experiences, blurring the lines between the physical and digital worlds. This will unlock new possibilities in training, design, and collaboration, where humans can interact with virtual environments as naturally as they do with physical ones. Moreover, these innovations will contribute to the creation of smart cities and intelligent transportation systems, where real-time data and AI-driven insights will lead to safer, more efficient, and sustainable urban environments.

This paper examines the role of 5G and secure edge networks in enabling these transformative technologies, focusing on their impact on smart technology campuses. By exploring key applications such as XR communication, vehicular communication, and UAV-based systems, we demonstrate how these advancements are leading to safer, more reliable, and more efficient solutions across various industries. Through the lens of a leading mobile network operator, this paper aims to provide insights into the future of industrial communication networks and the opportunities presented by the ongoing evolution toward the Industry 5.0 era.

The remainder of the manuscript is organized as follows: Section II explains four different use cases in practice together with their motivation about the need for a secure edge network and 5G technology. Section III concludes the paper.

II. USE CASES

A. XR-aided Co-design and Co-creation in B5G Secure Edge Network

The Fourth Industrial Revolution, commonly known as Industry 4.0, marks a significant transformation in industrial operations through the integration of advanced digital technologies to create smart, efficient, and interconnected sys-

tems. This transformative shift harnesses key innovations such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and automation, which are revolutionizing manufacturing and other industrial sectors. Nowadays, by incorporating these technologies, Industry 5.0 has started to pave the way for the development of intelligent factories, where production processes are optimized, productivity is enhanced, and real-time monitoring and data-driven decision-making are enabled with the orchestration of AI and autonomous systems.

A key enabler within Industry 4/5.0 is Extended Reality (XR), which offers immersive experiences applicable to various industrial contexts, particularly in collaborative product design. XR allows teams to collaborate within shared virtual spaces, regardless of their physical locations, thereby accelerating design processes and improving the final product quality. Furthermore, XR plays a pivotal role in training, remote assistance, and maintenance, contributing to the flexibility, adaptability, and overall efficiency of Industry 4/5.0-driven initiatives.

To meet the evolving needs of customers across the entire product development lifecycle from concept creation to industrial production—co-creation and virtual prototyping have gained prominence. The emergence of XR applications has opened up exciting possibilities, particularly for Beyond 5G (B5G) technologies [2]. XR enables geographically distributed teams to collaborate in real-time, facilitating innovation and shared outcomes throughout the design and development process. In these scenarios, edge computing technologies are critical, offering the high bandwidth and low latency necessary to support enhanced XR interactions across various locations [3]. This capability accelerates product design, reducing time-to-market and enabling faster customer feedback.

Secure edge network thus enhances user satisfaction in co-design environments by powering innovative XR applications tailored to vertical industries, such as smart manufacturing. These applications enable collaborative factory design and virtual product prototyping. As rendering and streaming processes shift from end devices to edge infrastructure, a robust, secure, and efficient data transfer network is essential. Although XR data is often stored in the cloud, computational tasks still predominantly occur on mobile devices, creating challenges in optimizing performance.

Our approach aims to address these challenges in the product development process by harnessing XR capabilities, B5G connectivity, and edge computing technologies. Specifically, we focus on creating a smart co-design environment within the household appliances industry by implementing adaptive edge computing mechanisms that automate the orchestration of underlying computing and networking resources. This integrated solution will streamline the new product development process, making it more responsive to market demands.

In the project VERGE, funded by the European Commission, the proposed architecture supports this use case by offering several critical capabilities across multiple layers, enhancing the efficiency, scalability, and security of XR-driven industrial applications [4]:

- Edge4AI Layer: This layer enables the offloading of

computationally intensive XR processes to edge computing resources, overcoming device-specific limitations in rendering large datasets. For instance, complex CAD files may consist of several million polygons, while standalone XR devices typically visualize only up to one million polygons effectively. To address this limitation, cloud-native middleware solutions at the application layer manage XR rendering and streaming. Additionally, advanced orchestration across single and multiple edge sites facilitates flexible deployment, scaling, and lifecycle management of XR software components, particularly as the number of end users (e.g., designers or robot operators) grows. Additionally, network slicing for industrial applications can be implemented using the user plane function at the edge to ensure lower latency.

- AI4Edge Layer: This layer integrates predictive analytics to forecast resource requirements and proactively allocate network slices, ensuring that the stringent latency and bandwidth demands of XR services are met. AI-driven resource management and real-time network function configuration leverage the system's ability to collect runtime metrics.
- Security and Privacy (SPT4AI Layer): Security and privacy are fundamental in industrial environments and are addressed at multiple levels of the architecture. To maximize privacy, scalability, and efficiency, distributed learning methods are employed, enabling local training without centralized data sharing. This approach dynamically allocates computation resources across the compute continuum. Additionally, smart defense mechanisms are implemented to mitigate the effects of malicious attacks targeting AI/ML models, particularly those that exploit vulnerabilities inherent in distributed and heterogeneous edge deployments.

This architecture not only boosts the performance of XR applications but also ensures the robustness and security of the system, making it well-suited for complex industrial use cases that demand high reliability and stringent privacy protections.

B. UAV-based network and airborne mobility

With the help of the evolving technologies in the industry and improved features such as low cost, small size, lightweight, high maneuverability, and quick deployment day by day, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), especially drones, have a wide range of use in military and also civil areas. The commercial usage purposes include numerous solo and multiple (swarm based) use cases in transport and transportation, smart agriculture, telecommunications, healthcare, video broadcasting, search and rescue, tracking, entertainment industry, etc. However, besides those benefits, the limited battery life and relatively short communication distance seem some challenging disadvantages in terms of mission requirements in today's technology [5]. To overcome these disadvantages, plenty of academic studies, conducted to be able to increase the advantages of these UAV systems by reducing their weak or unsatisfactory specifications, can be plethorically found in the literature. For instance, these works come up with

suggested solutions for charging difficulties, continuous and uninterrupted communication links, collision avoidance algorithms for swarm uses, data protection, and enhanced privacy against illegal interception during communication, etc.

In the light of these benefits mentioned, drones can provide useful solutions in the field of mobile and wireless communication with the help of their advanced features. Drones can be employed in critical missions such as, in times of emergency and disaster, when an existing terrestrial base station (BS) is out of service somehow. In this situation, a flying base station is quickly deployed on demand to create a coverage area or provide additional capacity and reduce traffic density in that area. Moreover, with their important advantages especially in flexible movement, deployment, and orbital mobility, such aerial vehicles can be exploited in the low-cost wireless communication applications such as flying antenna in mm-Wave communication, IoT communication, flying user equipment with cellular network connection, flying ad-hoc networks, flying backhaul for terrestrial networks, and smart cities [6].

In recent years, the rise of both academic and industrial attention on these UAV-based communication topics results in that drones officially come into the 3GPP 5G standards with Release 17 as an indication of the importance and need of drone communication in the next generation systems. In the context of drone communication, payload communication, and command and control communication should be mentioned as well. For payload communication, examples can be given such as video transfer, sensor data transfer (which requires high data transfer rates), command and control data required for remote control of the drone, and telemetry data such as autonomous flight or Beyond Visual Line-of-Sight (BVLOS) pilot control which requires lower data transfer rates but ultra-high reliability as well as low latency for safe operations [7].

Due to the difficulties caused by the mobility and different communication requirements of UAVs and terrestrial users in the same network, the authors in [8] discuss the usage of drones in terrestrial LTE networks, especially in different environmental environments (urban, sub-urban, rural, etc.) and at different altitudes.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, Turkcell aims to utilize UAV-based communication in secure edge networks such as smart construction, smart manufacturing, as well as smart surveillance sites requiring 5G connectivity for their field operations. Within the project ADACORSA, funded by European Commission and The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK), different airborne cellular coverage scenarios have been tested and evaluated based on the vertical measurements performed during the flying drone tests [9].

In addition, both tethered and mobile drone platforms have been compared in terms of flying duration, altitude, battery, coverage performance, etc. As expected, the results reveal that tethered drones can be used for longtime operations in a specific location though they serve in a more limited area. Furthermore, for the drone-based cellular communication systems to be useful and efficient, e.g. to have sufficient

coverage, to serve the appropriate number of users, to avoid any decrease or interruption in the quality of service provided or received, the accompanying difficulties, and analyses have been also investigated within this project.

C. Secure Edge Network in the 5G Technology Campus

In recent years, the integration of 5G technologies into secure edge networks has become a critical research area, driven by the increasing demand for low-latency, high-security, and reliable communications. The shift toward decentralized processing, particularly through edge computing, offers substantial advantages in supporting various industrial and enterprise applications that require real-time responsiveness and data privacy. With the deployment of 5G standalone (SA) networks at technology campuses, such as the one established in our study with 5 gNodeBs and 9 sectors, there has been a unique opportunity to explore the potential of edge-based applications in diverse use cases.

One prominent use case in this context is the implementation of secure Industrial IoT (IIoT) at the edge. By leveraging 5G technology to connect sensors, automation systems, and robotics, data can be processed locally at the edge, resulting in significantly reduced latency and increased security. This approach minimizes the exposure of sensitive information to external networks while enabling real-time decision-making, which is essential in industries where even milliseconds of delay can impact operational efficiency. Moreover, the deployment of private 5G networks on campus provides an additional layer of security by ensuring that critical data remains within a controlled environment, aligning with regulatory compliance needs in sectors like healthcare and finance.

Beyond IIoT, edge-based AI systems can be deployed to enhance cybersecurity in real-time. These AI models, operating at the edge, can detect and respond to potential cyber threats by analyzing network traffic and identifying anomalies without the delay associated with cloud processing. Similarly, secure edge networks are pivotal in remote work and education applications, where maintaining data integrity and confidentiality is paramount. The combination of localized data processing, robust security measures, and low-latency communication creates a foundation for future secure edge deployments, positioning 5G technologies as essential enablers of next-generation secure communication networks.

On the other hand, a 5G-enabled secure edge network can support intelligent transportation systems by allowing vehicles to communicate directly with nearby edge servers in the technology campus. Therefore, the security aspect is equally crucial in vehicular communications. Autonomous and connected vehicles are prime targets for cyber attacks, and a secure edge network can provide a decentralized layer of protection. By processing sensitive data locally at the edge, the risk of data breaches and attacks is reduced, and the vehicles can maintain secure communication channels with minimal exposure to external threats. This capability supports not only the safety of individual vehicles but also the overall integrity of the transportation network.

Fig. 1: UAV-based communication use case: BVLoS connectivity with the 5G capable tethered-drone and edge computer for the smart construction.

D. Fault and Accident Prevention of Oil Refineries in 6G Smart City Applications

As illustrated in Fig. 2, one of the main application and usage scenarios of 6G smart cities can be fault and accident prevention in refinery areas by real-time monitoring of large-area through both thermal closed-circuit TV (CCTV) cameras in land-area and drone cameras in sea-area during discharging the product and smooth approaching the dock-area, respectively. With the upcoming 6G wireless technology, the existing capabilities are expected to improve data rates, latency, network capacity, connection density, location accuracy, etc. The newly defined set of capabilities including energy efficiency in relation to sustainability, determinism, signal availability for ubiquitous coverage, and AI / ML is expected to be revolutionary metrics in 6G [10]. The expected technological advancements in 6G are going to improve and replace the manufactured operations in large areas like refineries by providing ultra-low latency and high-bandwidth consuming real-time high-resolution video broadcasting. Thus, the refinery area can be controlled intelligently over real-time monitoring and fast data transfer in 6G networks to provide more reliable land and sea area safety.

In the refinery area, it is important to have safe discharge of crude vessels in line with zero-waste processes in the sustainable world to prevent environmental pollution. Therefore, in this use case, real-time fault detection using 5G-Advanced/6G networks is considered an industrial implementation where it can be a good candidate for human-machine collaboration, which is expected to provide a high level of autonomy via advanced AI/ML techniques and integration. This use case focuses on the real-time or near-real-time detection of possible accidents in refineries like loss-leakage during oil transfer and fire risks of staff personnel. These faults can be categorized into four main categories, namely, fire, marine pollution, ship-docking error, and labour injuries.

Consequently, the relevant technologies must be designed effectively to overcome potential accidents. This can be achieved through the combination of emergency response due

to real-time monitoring, warning systems, and health and safety control mechanisms. This will serve not only sustainability key value indicator (KVI) through waste reduction but also AI-related applicable capabilities as a key performance indicator (KPI) for distributed high-bandwidth data processing (i.e., high-quality video streaming for surveillance).

In the port-surveillance use case, the land side is monitored by thermal CCTV cameras while the seaside is monitored by drones equipped with 5G advanced customer premises equipment (CPE) with high-fly duration capabilities. The seamless video images recorded on CCTV and drone cameras are transferred via fixed wired lines and 5G advanced wireless communication to the edge server and NR gNB, respectively. Then, the NR base station communicates with the core network over the transport network to provide end-to-end high-quality drone image transfer. 4K and thermal land-area images and seaside drone images are combined in the AI-empowered edge server to store and process the data for possible fault detection where AI/ML is applied whether an accident occurs. If there is any fault-detection exists, the health and safety flag reports the alarm for precautions in emergency cases, and then, the crisis or control centre activates the first responders to interfere in the accident area.

III. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated the significant role of 5G and 6G technologies, particularly when coupled with secure edge networks, in shaping the future of industrial communication and smart technology campuses. By examining the practical applications of these technologies, such as XR-aided co-design, UAV-based communications, and fault prevention in smart city environments, we have highlighted how next-generation networks can enhance safety, efficiency, and reliability across various domains. These advancements are pushing the boundaries of Industry 4.0 and paving the way for Industry 5.0, where human-machine collaboration becomes the centerpiece of innovation. Specifically, we have seen how these technologies enable smarter manufacturing, more intelli-

Fig. 2: Oil refinery use case: Fault detection via real-time monitoring with fixed CCTV cameras and beyond 5G capable drone cameras.

gent transportation systems, and safer industrial environments, leveraging advanced AI-driven decision-making and seamless data connectivity.

Looking ahead, as 6G networks further mature, we anticipate even greater levels of autonomy, AI integration, and ubiquitous connectivity. This will support increasingly sophisticated applications, enhancing not only industrial productivity but also societal well-being. However, challenges remain, particularly regarding the optimization of edge computing resources, ensuring data privacy, and securing communications in highly dynamic environments like UAV networks.

In conclusion, the continued development and deployment of 5G and 6G technologies within secure edge networks will be fundamental in transforming both current and future industries, driving a new era of technological collaboration and innovation. The use cases presented in this paper demonstrate the vast potential for 5G/6G to deliver tangible benefits in various fields, underlining the importance of ongoing research and development to fully realize these opportunities.

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